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UNUSUAL FAUNISTIC COLLECTION FROM THE SCIENTIFIC FUNDS OF THE NATIONAL KYIV-PECHERSK RESERVE

Animal bones were discovered in Scientific funds in National Kyiv-Pechersk Reserve. There are 17 pieces. We present here their identification and the description of taphonomic observations. These bones belong to *Mammuthus primigenius*, *Ursus sp.* and *Cervus sp.* They come from various sites from Ukraine. Probably, this collection was formed in the National Kyiv-Pechersk Reserve as a result of the return of materials from Ukrainian museums after the Second World War.

Keywords: National Kyiv-Pechersk Reserve, Illinka Cave, Kyrylivska site, returned collections.

INTRODUCTION

In 2017, a faunal collection based on mammoth bones was accidentally discovered in the Scientific Funds of the National Kyiv-Pechersk Reserve. Of course, the question of the origin of this collection

immediately arose. Upon initial examination of this material, it immediately became clear that the bones came from different locations or sites.

In September 2017, the collection was analyzed by Laëtitia Demay (table 1).

Table 1. Inventory. / **Табл. 1.** Склад фауністичної збірки.

N°	Notes	N° bis	TAXON	ELEMENT	Lat.
1 and 2			<i>Mammuthus</i>	tusk	/
3 and 12			<i>Mammuthus</i>	humerus	dext
4			<i>Mammuthus</i>	humerus	dext
5			<i>Mammuthus</i>	mandible	
6		3139	<i>Mammuthus</i>	ulna	sin
7			<i>Ursus sp.</i>	femur	dext
8			<i>Mammuthus</i>	humerus	dext
9			<i>Cervidae (Cervus sp.)</i>	skull and antler	sin
10	llinka	73	<i>Ursus sp.</i>	humerus	sin
11			<i>C. elaphus</i>	antler	dext
13		3169	<i>Mammuthus</i>	ulna	sin
14			<i>C. elaphus</i>	skull and antler. slaughter antler ; median antler ; part of palms	dext
15			<i>Ursus sp.</i>	mandible + root fragments of 3 molars	dext
16			<i>Mammuthus</i>	upper molar	sin
17			<i>Mammuthus</i>	upper molar	sin

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METHODS

We processed to the paleontological identification (species and anatomical elements) and taphonomical analyses (Efremov 1940; Behrensmeyer 1978; Denys, Patou-Mathis 2014).

The measurements of bones were made according to the methods applied on mammals and particularly Elephantids developed by Von den Driesch (1976), Agenbroad (1994) and Averianov (1996). The material used is a flexible tape measure, a rigid tape measure and a 150 mm caliper.

Concerning *Ursus* sp., we used Weinstock (2009) for determination of ages and Petronio, di Canzio and di Stefano (2003) to distinct species by morphometry.

Concerning mammoth, age classes were estimated from the growth stages of long bones (Laws 1966; Krumrey, Buss 1968; Hanks 1972; Haynes 1991; Lister 1999) and teeth (Osborn 1942; Vaufrey 1955; Coppens 1965; Shoshaniand, Tassy 1996).

To identify if these bones belong to *M. primigenius*, and determine the sex, we used data obtained about other known specimens (table 2).

Table 2. Specimens of *Mammuthus primigenius* used for osteometric comparisons.

Табл. 2. Зразки *Mammuthus primigenius*, що використовуються для остеометричних порівнянь.

Individual	Year of discovery	Locality	Age	Sex	Height at the withers (in cm)	Chronology and dates	References
Rottweil	1967	Germany, Bade-Wurtemberg	>25 y.o.	F	250	End of Upper Pleistocene	Ziegler, 2001
Kastykhtakh	2008	Russia, Taymir	38-45 y.o.	F	224	32 070-30 565 BP	Kirillova et al., 2012
Oyesh river	1988-1991	Russia, Siberia	adults.l.	F	215 (240)	~14 000 BP	Averianov, 1994
Sanga-Yuryakh	1908	Russia, Yakoutia	54-60 y.o.	F	/	39 000-37 000 BP	Vollosovich, 1909 Garrut, 1964
Aa = Arques	1908	France, Pas-de-Calais	40-50 y.o.	F but size of M	301	Middle-Upper Pleistocene	Pontier, 1913
Ahlen	1910	Germany, North Rhine-Westphalia	31-34 y.o.	M	320	41 000 BP	Siegfried, 1959
Borna	1908-1909	Germany, Saxony	25-30 y.o.	M	320	Upper Pleistocene	Felix, 1912
Polch	1936	Germany, Rhineland-Palatinate	60-70 y.o.	M	320	Upper Pleistocene	Koenigswald, 1989
Pfännerhall	1953	Germany, Saxony-Anhalt	~60 y.o.	M	300	Saalian	Toepfer, 1957
Siegsdorf	1975	Germany, Upper Bavaria	49->52 y.o.	M	360	47 000 BP	Ziegler, 1994
Condover	1986	Great Britain, Shropshire	28 y.o.	M	/	14 000 BP	Lister, 2009
Lena (= Adams)	1799	Russia, Siberia	43-50 y.o.	M	320	34 450 ± 2 500 BP	Adams, 1808 Pfitzenmayer, 1907
Berezovka	1900	Russia, Siberia	30-35 y.o.	M	265	End of Upper Pleistocene	Pfitzenmayer, 1926
Lyakhov (= Atrikanova ou Vollossovitch)	1914	Russia, Lyakhov islands	~30 y.o.	M	/	49 000 BP	Coppens, 1958 Vollossovich, 1914 Viola, 2014
Taimyr	1948	Russia, Taimyr	50-55 y.o.	M	265	11 450 ± 250 BP	Garrut et Dubinin, 1951
Sevsk	1988-1991	Russia, Siberia	adults.l.	M	235	~14 000	Vereshagin, Tikhonov, 1986 Maschenko et al., 2006

DESCRIPTION AND RESULTS

n°1 and n°2

It is a tusk (fig. 1), that we can not lateralized for sure.

This tusk seems to belong to *Mammuthus primi-*

genius. Moreover, according to the measurements this tusk belongs to a male (fig. 2).

This tusk is relatively well preserved. The surface is covered by manganese and ferric deposits related to post-depositional water percolation.

▲ Fig. 1. Tusk of mammoth.
Рис. 1. Бивень мамонта.

◀ Fig. 2. Measurements of *M. primigenius* tusks.
Рис. 2. Морфологічні показники бивнів *M. primigenius*.
female ■ male □

n°3 and n°12

It is a distal end and a diaphysis of a right humerus (fig. 3).

According to measurements (fig. 4) this humerus could belong to a female. The distal end is fused, so this individual was more than stage XVla (> 18-26 years old).

The coloration is white. The surface is exfoliated and presents plant root marks. So these bone could stay in open air, then buried in subsurface.

n°4

It is a diaphysis of a right humerus (fig. 5).

Extremities are not fused, so this individual is a young adult less than stage XVla (< 18-26 years old). Moreover, this humerus is characterized by a pathology.

The surface is covered by manganese deposits and plant root marks.

▲ **Fig. 3.** Right humerus of mammoth in anterior view.
 Рис. 3. Права плечова кістка мамонта. Вигляд спереду.

▼ **Fig. 4.** Osteometry of humerus of mammoths.
 Рис. 4. Остеометрія плечової кістки мамонтів.

n°5

It is a fragment of mandible of mammoth (fig. 6).

This mandible could belong to a male (fig. 7).

The surface is covered by manganese deposits and plant root marks.

n°6

It is a left ulna of mammoth (fig. 8).

The bone is too damaged for reliable measurements. The distal end is fused so this individual is an adult more than stage XVIIIa-XX (> 25-35 years old)

if it is a female and more than stage XXII-XXX (> 36 years old) if it is a male.

The surface is very damaged, with exfoliation, removal of cortical bone and fissurations due to weathering. So this bone stayed in open air and then was recovered by sediments containing manganese deposits.

The proximal part of diaphysis was burned.

An indistinct inscription is visible on the surface, probably in pencil — “№3139”.

Fig. 7. Internal widths of the mandibular symphysis of mammoths.
Рис. 7. Внутрішня ширина між симфізами нижньої щелепи мамонтів.

Fig. 5. Right humerus of mammoth in lateral view.
Рис. 5. Права плечова кістка мамонта. Вигляд збоку.

Fig. 6. Mandible of mammoth in occlusal view.
Рис. 6. Нижня щелепа мамонта. Вигляд з внутрішньої сторони.

Fig. 8. Left ulna of mammoth in anterior view.
Рис. 8. Ліва ліктьова кістка мамонта. Вигляд спереду.

Fig. 9. Right femur of *Ursus* sp. in posterior view.
Рис. 9. Права стегнова кістка *Ursus* sp. Вигляд з тильної сторони.

n°7

It is a right femur of an adult bear (fig. 9).

The distal end is fused so this individual is an adult more than 6 years old. The surface presents plant root marks, also as marks due to *charrriage-à-sec* and/or trampling and manganese and ferric deposits. So this bone was altered by soil movements. Moreover, a red chemical product was applied to consolidate this bone and several recent tool marks were observed.

n°8

It is a right humerus of mammoth (fig. 10).

The proximal part is fused so this individual is an adult more than stage XVla (> 18-26 years old) if it

is a female and more than stage XVIIIa-XX (> 25-35 years old) if it is a male.

The surface is covered by manganese deposits and plant root marks. Moreover, the proximal part is covered by red color deposits.

n°9

It is a part of a right antler with a fragment of skull of *Cervidae* (*Cervus sp.*) (fig. 11).

The surface is a little bit exfoliated and presents a little bit of manganese and ferric deposits.

n°10

It is a left humerus of an adult bear (fig. 12). The note "с. Илинка" and "№73" is mentioned on this bone.

▲ Fig. 10. Right humerus of mammoth in anterior view.
Рис. 10. Права плечова кістка мамонта. Вигляд спереду.

Fig. 11. Right antler with part of skull of *Cervidae*.
Рис. 11. Правий ріг з частиною черепа *Cervidae*. ▲

▲ Fig. 12. Left humerus of *Ursus sp.* in posterior view.
Рис. 12. Ліва плечова кістка *Ursus sp.* Вигляд з тильної сторони.

The distal end is fused so this individual is an adult more than 4 years old. Concerning the distal end, the medio-lateral diameter is 110 mm. So it is situated in the confusion zone between *U. spelaeus* and *U. arctos* (fig. 13).

According to the morphology it looks more like *U. spelaeus* (fig. 14).

The surface presents plant root marks, also as marks due to *charriage-à-sec* and/or trampling and manganese and ferric deposits. So this bone was altered by soil movements.

Moreover, a red chemical product was applied to consolidate this bone.

n°11

It is a fragment of a right antler of *Cervus sp.* (fig. 15).

The surface is a little bit exfoliated and presents a little bit of manganese and ferric deposits. There are many marks of modern tools.

n°13

It is a left ulna of mammoth (fig. 16).

Fig. 13. Measurements of the distal end of humerus between *U. spelaeus* and *U. arctos*, compared with bone of bear n°10.

Рис. 13. Метричні показники дистального кінця плечової кістки *U. spelaeus* та *U. arctos*, порівняно з кісткою ведмедя №10.

According to the dimensions of this ulna, it could belong to a female (fig. 17). Whether it is a male or a female, this individual was an adult more than stage XVIIIa-XX (> 25-35 years old).

The surface is exfoliated and presents marks due to *charriage-à-sec* and/or trampling. So this bone was altered by soil movements. Moreover, the proximal part is covered by red color deposits.

On the bone there is a postage stamp with an ink number — “3169” (fig. 16b). At the end of the 19th — beginning of the 20th century, during the documentation process of museum collections, it was a common practice to stick a stamp with an inventory number according to the inventory book on a collectible item. According to the inventory book (catalog) of the Archaeological Museum of Kyiv University, which is preserved in the fund “Museum of Antiquities of the University of St. Vladimir” (NA IA NAS of Ukraine, f. 13, d. 94) numbers “3103-3187” were given to “bone objects found in pit-dwelling on Kirillovskaya street, No. 61” (on Russian) (sheets 49 verso — 50). It is reasonable to assume that bone No. 13 comes from the collection of the Kyrylivska Paleolithic site.

Fig. 14. Distal end of humerus in posterior view (Petronio, di Canzio and di Stefano 2003). A : *U. spelaeus*; B : *U. arctos*.

Рис. 14. Дистальний кінець плечової кістки. Вигляд з тильної сторони (Petronio, di Canzio and di Stefano 2003).

A : *U. spelaeus*; B : *U. arctos*.

Fig. 15. Fragment of right antler of *Cervus sp.*

Рис. 15. Фрагмент правого рогу *Cervus sp.* ▼

Fig. 16. Left ulna of mammoth in anterior view (a); postage stamp with an ink number (b).

Рис. 16. Ліва ліктьова кістка мамонта, вид спереду (a); марка з номером (b). ►

Measurements of proximal end

Fig. 17. Osteometry of ulna of mammoths.
Рис. 17. Остеометрія ліктьової кістки мамонтів.

n°14

It is a right antler with a fragment of skull of an adult *Cervus elaphus* (fig. 18).

The surface is exfoliated and presents deposits of manganese.

n°15

It is a right hemi-mandible of bear with roots of three molars (fig. 19).

The surface is exfoliated due to weathering and presents plant root marks.

Fig. 18. Right antler with part of skull of *Cervus elaphus* in lateral view. ▶

Рис. 18. Правий ріг з частиною черепа *Cervus elaphus*. Вигляд збоку.

Fig. 19. Right hemi-mandible of *Ursus* sp. in lingual view.

Рис. 19. Права половина нижньої щелепи *Ursus* sp. Лінгвальна сторона. ▼

n°16

It is a left upper molar (fig. 20).

According to the laminar frequency and the width of enamel it is a *Mammuthus primigenius*. According to the dimensions and the number of plates it is a M³ which belongs to a matured adult (stages XXI-XXII — 35-45 years old) (table 3).

Fig. 20. Left upper molar of *Mammuthus primigenius*.
Рис. 20. Лівий верхній моляр *Mammuthus primigenius*.

n°17

It is a left upper molar (fig. 21).

According to the laminar frequency and the width of enamel it is a *Mammuthus primigenius*. According to the dimensions and the number of plates it is a M² or a M³ which belongs to an adult (table 3).

Fig. 21. Left upper molar of *Mammuthus primigenius*.
Рис. 21. Лівий верхній моляр *Mammuthus primigenius*.

Table 3. Data about molars of mammoth.

Табл. 3. Характеристики молярів мамонта.

N°	Lat.	Number of plates	Eruption and wear stages	Laminar frequency	Width of enamel (in mm)	Mesio-distal diameter occ. (in mm)	Vestibulo-lingual diameter occ. (in mm)	Mesio-distal diameter tot. (in mm)
16	G	19	x, 8E, 4D, 7C*	8	1,8	171	88	260
17	G	14	/	8	1	173	76	232

* (E : used; D : few used; C : erupting).

* (E : спрацьований; D : ледь спрацьований; C : той, що прорізується).

SYNTHESIS

This assemblage is composed of at least six individuals:

- 1 bear (adult *s.l.*)
- 2 *Cervus sp.* (male adult *s.l.*)
- 3 mammoths (1 female adult *s.l.* ; 1 male adult *s.l.*, 1 young adult)

According to the taphonomic observations, it seems to have at least three different assemblages.

DISCUSSION

We are certain of the presence of elements from Illinka (fig. 22).

Concerning some other bones, they could come from Kyrylivska site (fig. 22), according to the taphonomic observations on bones which are similar with those of the material preserved in the National Museum of History of Ukraine and archival research.

Odesa region is characterized by the presence of natural karst cavities. In 1938 T. Grytsai discovered and excavated the Illinka Cave (Підоплічко 1949) (fig. 23). A large number of animal bones and flint

fragments were found (Пощін 1939; 1941). T. Grytsai and O. Dobrovolskyi (1950) led excavations between 1939 and 1945. Stone material is not abundant and is represented by processed flints and quartzite. The collection is subdivided into three complexes of different times, among which the earliest is the most numerous. Most often, researchers considered it most likely that it belongs to the Middle Paleolithic, but there were other assumptions (Замятнін 1950; Ефименко 1953; 1954; Сапожников, Сапожникова 1989). The geological position of this site was described by K.K. Pronin (1999). Besides stone tools some bone polishers and drilled bear canines were found. One of the bone tools was 14C dated to 27.500 ± 210 BP (Ki-11681) (Сапожников 2005). Another date was furnished about bear bone to 41.700 ± 1200 (VERA-2195) (Kavcik-Graumann *et al.* 2016). This cave was probably alternated between humans and bears. The fauna of Illinka cave (MNI: 468; NR: 29971) (Підоплічко 1956; Ridush, 2009) includes mainly cave bear remains (MNI: 374; NR: 29336), then cave hyaena, wolf, red fox, corsac fox, badger, cave

lion, naked mole-rat, european hamster, porcupine, hare, pika, horse, woolly rhinoceros, bison, saiga antelope, roe deer and red deer (fig. 24).

In the beginning of 2000, a cooperation between the university of Vienna and the Museum of Odesa permitted to study cave bear remains (Kavcik-Graumann *et al.* 2016). The authors conclude that the cave bears of the Illinka cave belong to *Ursus*

ingressus. It was a massive herbivorous (Bocherens *et al.* 2011) cave bear larger than *U. spelaeus* which weight was estimated around 350 kg to 600 kg; it lived in Central and Eastern Europe within continental environments with cold and arid climate (Rabeder *et al.* 2004). Some researchers still question them to be different species, but rather subspecies (Baca *et al.* 2012).

Fig. 23. Geographic position of the site of Illinka (Ukraine) (Kavcik-Graumann *et al.* 2016 after Nagel *et al.* 2005).

Рис. 23. Географічне розташування стоянки Іллінка (Україна) (Kavcik-Graumann *et al.* 2016 за Nagel *et al.* 2005).

Fig. 24. Faunal spectrum of Illinka (Ukraine) in percentage (after data from Підоплічко 1956; Ridush 2009).

Рис. 24. Фауністичний спектр Іллінки (Україна) у відсотках (за даними Підоплічко 1956; Ridush 2009).

Concerning the site of Kyrylivska, it is situated in Kyiv (fig. 25) on a promontory, on the right bank of the Dnieper (Шидловський, Прядко 2011). This site was discovered and excavated in 1893 to 1900 by V. Khvoika. He highlighted that lithic remains are anthropogenic product and that these tools were associated with mammoth bones (1913, re-edited in 2008). Some of these tusks presented also anthropogenic modifications (Беяшевский 1900; Волков 1903; Абрамова 1962; Филиппов 1983). The archaeological remains were in clayey sand (Громов 1948). It could have one cultural layer (Пидопличко 1969) or, more likely, two (Хвойка 1913 (2008); Борисковский 1953) (fig. 26).

A 14C date from mammoth teeth was obtained to $19\,200 \pm 250$ BP (OxA-718) (Абрамова, Grigorieva and Zaitsev, 2001; Радієвська, Біленко 2010).

The lithic industry has been studied repeatedly (Вовк 1899a; 1899b; Хвойка 1913(2008); Борисковский 1941; 1953; Ефименко 1953; Гладких 1971;1991; Шидловський 2012). The upper layer is the richest with 3000 lithic remains and burned bones. The lower layer furnished 250 lithic remains. Both correspond to characteristics of Upper Palaeolithic industries. P.S. Shydlovskiy and D.V. Stupak revised the material in 2015, based on lithic material kept at the National Museum of Ukrainian History and the Museum of Saint-Germain-en-Laye (France) and on analysis of the work of predecessors. For them, the lithic productions in the two layers are similar to the processes of debiting and shaping. However, the composition of the tools differs. The industry could correspond to later Gravettian (Shydlovskiy, Stupak 2015).

Unfortunately, the distribution of remains is poorly known because there were no recorded during excavations. The fauna of Kyrylivska (MNI: 79; NR: 454) (Хвойка 1913 (2008); Пидопличко 1969) includes mainly woolly mammoth remains (MNI: 70; NR: 440), then woolly rhinoceros, wolf, brown bear, cave lion, cave hyaena, wolverine and the presence of hare was mentioned (fig. 27).

We had access to only a few pieces still kept at the National Museum of Ukrainian History. The taphonomic observations are similar with some bones of this collection, especially concerning bones n°6 and n°13.

Fig. 25. Localisation of Kyrylivska in Kyiv (after Pidoplichko 1998).

Рис. 25. Локалізація Кирилівської стоянки у Києві (за Pidoplichko 1998).

Fig. 26. Excavations and geology in Kyrylivska (Хвойка 1893; Хвойка 1913), with two cultural layers.

Рис. 26. Розкопки та геологічна ситуація Кирилівської стоянки (Хвойка 1893; Хвойка 1913), з двома культурними шарами.

Fig. 27. Faunal spectrum of Kyrylivska (Ukraine) in percentage (after data from Хвойка 1913; Пидопличко 1969).

Рис. 27. Фауністичний спектр Кирилівської стоянки (Україна) у відсотках (за даними Хвойка 1913; Пидопличко 1969).

Fig. 28. Bone n°13 (mammoth ulna) with colored deposits.

Рис. 28. Кістка № 13 (ліктьова кістка мамонта) з кольоровим забарвленням.

The colored deposits were not previously described in literature. They are orange-red-brown (fig. 28). They are present on both cortical bone and spongy bone, so they were deposited when the bones were already dry. They could have varied composition (alumino-silicates, ferruginous sandstone, hematite, crinoidal limestone, manganese oxides, iron oxide crystals, ocher sands such as kaolin and bauxite, goethite...) and have different origins (meteorological, biological and pedosedimentary impacts/anthropic implication) (Delamare, 1987; Salomon, 2009; Ardouin, 2012).

Thanks to the study of archival data, it became possible to trace the likely path that these bones took to the National Kyiv-Pechersk Reserve. As a result of the institutional restructuring of the museum network in the late 1920s — during the 1930s, the archaeological collections of Kyiv, including paleontological finds, were concentrated in the Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra. In particular, in the early 1930's there was an Archaeological Museum of the Ukrainian Academy of Sciences, in 1934-1935 the All-Ukrainian Historical Museum was moved here (from September 11, 1935 — the Central Historical Museum). As of 1936, the archeological complexes of the Central Historical Museum contained the collections of the former All-Ukrainian Historical Museum named after T. Shevchenko in Kyiv, the Archaeological Museum of Kyiv University, the Archaeological Cabinet of the Kyiv Institute of Public Education, the Archaeological Museum of Higher Women's Courses in Kyiv and the Archaeological Museum of the Ukrainian Academy of Sciences.

Paleolithic materials were presented in the Central Historical Museum by collections of sites: Kyrylivska (excavations by V. Khvoika in 1893-1900), Iskorost (excavations by V. Khvoika in 1911), Mizyn (excavations by Kh. Vovk in 1908, M. Rudynskyi in the 1930s), Zhuravka (excavations by M. Rudynskyi in 1929). In addition, the outskirts of dif-

ferent villages were presented: Kostyonki (research by O. Kelsiev), Karacharov (research of V. Antonovych, I. Polyakov and V. Dokuchaev in 1878), Vrublevtsi, complexes of materials from locations near the villages Studenytsia (research by V. Antonovych in the 1880s, M. Rudynskyi and M. Musket in 1927-28), Stara Ushytsia (research by M. Rudynskyi and M. Mushket 1927-28) and near Novhorod-Siverskyi (research by M. Rudynskyi in 1925-26).

At the beginning of the Second World War, a part of the collections of the Central Historical Museum were evacuated, but some pieces were left on the territory of the Kyiv-Pechersk Lavra. Later, a part of the remaining collection was transferred to the National Museum of Prehistory and Early History in Kyiv, and in 1943 — taken to Germany.

After the Second World War, some displaced collections returned in Kyiv. The distribution of these artifacts between museum institutions of the country partly took place on the territory of the Kyiv-Pechersk Reserve. Most of the archaeological collections were transferred to the State Historical Museum, which was restored in 1944. Today, they are part of the Scientific funds of the National Museum of History of Ukraine.

Probably the found collection got to the territory of the National Kyiv-Pechersk Reserve in the postwar period due to the return of materials of Ukrainian museums.

CONCLUSIONS

The collection contains bones of at least six individuals:

- 1 bear (adult *s.l.*)
- 2 *Cervus sp.* (male adult *s.l.*)
- 3 mammoths (1 female adult *s.l.*; 1 male adult *s.l.*, 1 young adult).

This collection contains bones from different places of origin. According to the taphonomic observations, it seems belong at least three different assemblages. There is no doubt about the origin from the Illinka Cave, with a very high degree of probability — from the Kyrylivska site, this probability is especially high for bones No. 13 and 6.

The red coloration deposits (ochre?) observed of some bones would require the advice of a specialist.

Most likely, this collection was formed in the Scientific funds of the National Kyiv-Pechersk Reserve because of the return of materials from Ukrainian museums after the Second World War.

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НЕЗВИЧАЙНА ФАУНІСТИЧНА КОЛЕКЦІЯ З НАУКОВИХ ФОНДІВ НАЦІОНАЛЬНОГО КИЄВО-ПЕЧЕРСЬКОГО ЗАПОВІДНИКА

У 2017 р. у Наукових фондах Національного Києво-Печерського заповідника випадково виявлено фауністичну колекцію з 17 кісток. Основою її були кістки мамонта. Звісно, одразу постало питання про походження цієї збірки. Після первинного огляду цього матеріалу стало зрозумілим, що кістки походять з різних місцезнаходжень. У вересні 2017 року колекцію проаналізувала Летісія Демей (таблиця 1).

Ці кістки належать, як мінімум шести особинам — 1 *Ursus sp.*; 2 — *Cervus sp.*; 3 — *Mammuthus primigenius*. Згідно з тафономічними спостереженнями, здається, що вони належать принаймні до трьох різних сукупностей.

Немає жодних сумнівів щодо походження кістки ведмедя з печери Іллінка, про що свідчить шифр, який на ній зберігся. З дуже високим ступенем ймовірності походження деяких кісток з Кирилівської стоянки. Ця ймовірність особливо висока для кісток No 13 та 6.

Червоні забарвлення (вохра?), які спостерігаються на деяких кістках, потребують консультації фахівця.

Завдяки вивченню архівних даних стало можливим простежити ймовірний шлях, яким ці кістки потрапили до Національного Києво-Печерського заповідника. Після Другої світової війни одним із центрів повернення музейних експонатів, переміщених під час війни, був Київ. Розподілення цих колекцій між музейними установами країни частково відбувалося на території Києво-Печерського заповідника. Більшість археологічних колекцій було передано до Державного історичного музею, який був відновлений у 1944 р. Сьогодні вони є частиною Наукових фондів Національного музею історії України.

Ймовірно, знайдена колекція сформувалась на території Національного Києво-Печерського заповідника і залишилась у Наукових фондах у повоєнний період, у процесі повернення матеріалів українських музеїв.

Ключові слова: Національний Києво-Печерський заповідник, печера Іллінка, Кирилівська стоянка, повернені колекції.